

ISic3718

I.Sicily inscription 3718

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

(?)

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

collezione Recupero

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336682

1. πρόσβυ [ς] ἘΠΟСΒΥ, copy, Ferrara²

2. EINEAC

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 336682

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1199

Ferrara, F. 1829. Storia di Catania sino alla fine del secolo xviii. Catania. At 384 no.18

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 57 n.217

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